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**INVESTIGATION OF ENANTIODISCRIMINATION USING
DIFFUSION-NMR AND MULTISCALE SIMULATIONS**

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1 Introduction

Enantiomers are chiral compounds that exist as non-superimposable mirror images of each other.^{1,2} These species have similar physical and chemical properties except for their interaction with a polarized light plane or other chiral entities.³ This difference in interaction ensures great relevance and significant applications of these molecules across several fields, such as pharmaceuticals,^{4,5} agriculture,^{6,7} food,^{8,9} nanotechnology,^{10,11} and fragrances.^{12,13}

Among these, pharmaceuticals represent the most significant area of application, as the majority of marketed drugs are chiral. Recent analyses of the new approvals by the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) agency indicate that around 60% of new approved drugs are chiral, compared to approximately 40% for achiral ones.^{14,15} This is largely due to their higher potency, which often results in improved pharmacodynamic and pharmacokinetic profiles.¹⁶

Over the past decades, researchers have noted that stereoisomeric drugs can manifest more desirable biological activities. However, this is not universally true because some enantiomers may be therapeutically active, while others can be inactive or even harmful.^{16,17} The differences arise from stereospecific interactions with biological targets, which can result in distinct effects.¹⁸ Several well-known examples of enantiomeric drugs can be listed, such as ibuprofen and thalidomide. One of these is ketamine, in which the (*S*)-enantiomer exhibits anesthetic effects, while the (*R*)-form is associated with hallucinogenic activity.¹⁹ Hence, knowing the structure and biological activity of each enantiomer is a key point for the safe and effective use of chiral drugs.²⁰

In this regard, regulatory agencies such as the FDA and the European Medicines Agency (EMA) have established specific guidelines and regulations that require a comprehensive examination of properties and characterization of each enantiomer before market approval, ensuring their safety and efficacy.^{21,22} Nonetheless, the production, separation, and analysis of enantiomers is still a significant challenge in both experimental and theoretical research.

Given the importance of individual enantiomers, extensive research efforts have also focused on their production.^{23–25} Advances in this area were especially recognized by the Chemistry Nobel Prizes in 2001 (asymmetric catalysis) and 2021 (asymmetric organocatalysis), which shows the continuous interest in producing enantiomerically pure molecules.

The growing demand for chiral molecules, combined with their production at an unprecedented rate, has spurred an increasing number of investigations dedicated to developing methods for enantioanalysis. Thus, the rapid identification and quantification of enantiomeric mixtures have become indispensable and still persist as an analytical challenge, requiring innovative strategies to overcome the bottleneck in the speed of enantioresolution methods.²⁶

A range of techniques, such as chiral chromatography,²⁷ electronic and vibrational circular dichroism,²⁸ and x-ray crystallography²⁹, are employed to analyze enantiomers and provide their enantiomeric excess (*ee*) or the absolute configuration (*AC*). However, these approaches are often expensive, time-consuming, labor-intensive, and may require large sample quantities, prior enantiomeric separation, or computational support.^{30–32} As a result, there is a clear need for faster, more efficient, and accessible methods for enantiomeric resolution.

Nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy has emerged as a practical and powerful

tool for enantiomer analysis.²⁶ In principle, enantiomer mixtures in an achiral medium have completely overlapping NMR signals due to identical chemical environments. To resolve this degeneracy and differentiate them, a chiral entity is introduced, forming diastereomeric complexes with each enantiomer. If each stereoisomer experiences a different chemical environment, the signals will become distinct, resulting in chemical shift separation (frequency discrimination).

A wide range of chiral compounds - chiral resolving agents (CRAs) - has been employed for this purpose and are commonly grouped into chiral derivatizing agents (CDAs),³³ chiral shift reagents (CSRs),³⁴ and chiral solvating agents (CSAs).³⁵ CDAs typically undergo a chemical reaction, making subsequent direct recovery of the enantiomer unfeasible. In contrast, CSRs and CSAs interact non-covalently, either through metal complexation (CSRs) or solely intermolecular interactions such as hydrogen bonding (CSAs). These two types are often preferred due to their reversible complex formation, which allows for the easier recovery of the analyte.

Many types of CRAs have been explored, including cyclodextrins,³⁶ crown ethers,^{37,38} macrocyclic structures,³⁹ BINOL-based compounds,⁴⁰ and metal complexes.⁴¹ However, most of these are not commercially available or often require specialized syntheses. Moreover, enantiodiscrimination strategies frequently focus on measuring *ee* or simply resolving the signals, without providing any information on *AC*.^{26,42,43} This highlights the demand for NMR methods that are simple, cost-effective, and capable of assigning *AC* in solution.

A promising strategy is the combination of diffusion experiments (Diffusion-Ordered Spectroscopy - DOSY) with the Matrix-Assisted DOSY (MAD-DOSY) approach.^{38,44,45} In this strategy, a chiral matrix such as **BINOL** is added to the solution, forming selective diastereomeric complexes that modulate the chemical shifts and the diffusion behavior of each enantiomer. This allows not only frequency distinction but also diffusion separation.^{46,47}

Diffusion discrimination is important because it can provide valuable insights into the dynamics and molecular interactions of enantiomers. Although **BINOL** has been employed as a CSA to induce chemical shift differences, its small size and solubility issues (due to the higher amount required) make it insufficient for achieving measurable diffusion coefficient differences beyond the experimental error.⁴⁴ Additionally, no stereoselective trend in diffusion behavior has been clearly observed, limiting the *AC* determination.

A natural next step is the use of larger chiral environments, such as micellar systems. Several studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of surfactants in modulating diffusional behaviors, enabling the resolution of complex mixtures in a single experiment without prior physical separation.⁴⁸⁻⁵⁰ Therefore, chiral micelles can be especially interesting for resolving enantiomers simultaneously in frequency and diffusion dimensions.

Indeed, chiral micelles are already applied in other contexts where a chiral medium is required, such as chiral chromatography, to achieve physical separation of enantiomers.⁵¹ Moreover, these systems have also proven helpful in asymmetric catalysis, contributing to the synthesis of enantiomerically pure compounds.⁵² Thus, these surfactants represent a promising matrix candidate for the chiral MAD.

Motivated by the need to develop effective enantiodiscrimination and *AC* determination

strategies, this thesis introduces a novel NMR approach that combines chiral surfactants with diffusion experiments. The proposed CHiral Micelle Enantiomer Resolving Agents (**CHIMERA**) strategy offers a cost-effective and easy-to-handle matrix for enantiomer separation. Its applicability is demonstrated through the resolution of a broad range of enantiomers with diverse functional groups and molecular skeletons.

In addition to experimental studies, this thesis also proposes to integrate computational simulation into the investigations. While experiments provide key information on enantiomer-matrix interactions, they are often insufficient in fully elucidating the molecular mechanisms behind chiral recognition and enantiodifferentiation processes. From this perspective, computational methods can help to address this limitation by offering atomic-level insights into the structural, thermodynamic, and energetic factors that govern these chiral complexations.⁵³⁻⁵⁵

Computational approaches such as Molecular Dynamics (MD) simulations and Quantum Mechanical (QM) calculations have become indispensable for studying chiral systems.⁵⁶⁻⁵⁸ These methods have been shown to elucidate the dynamic behavior of chiral complexes and their interaction mechanisms behind the experimental observations.⁵⁹⁻⁶¹ They are also used to investigate solvation effects,⁶² enantioseparations,⁴⁰ and explore various enantioselectors.⁶³⁻⁶⁵

Although previous computational studies have examined chiral systems that were experimentally investigated by NMR, many of them focus on specific resolving agents, such as cyclodextrins or metal complexes.^{66,67} Moreover, recent studies have also employed simulations to examine enantiomer assignment using alignment media, rather than the commonly used NMR solution-state.^{68,69}

Furthermore, the literature lacks well-established protocols for simulating the diffusional behavior of diastereomeric complexes or elucidating the recognition process observed by NMR. Consequently, a significant knowledge gap remains in understanding chiral complexation mechanisms in solution. This underscores the need for further computational development in this field. Accordingly, this thesis also aims to establish robust theoretical workflows and perform detailed simulations to provide atomistic-level insights into the processes governing experimental enantiodiscrimination.

2 Objectives

The general goal was to develop a novel approach for enantiomer discrimination and absolute configuration assignment using diffusion NMR in the presence of chiral micelles. In addition, this thesis aimed to integrate experimental and computational methodologies to enhance molecular-level understanding and predict the chiral recognition mechanisms behind the observed enantiodifferentiations.

2.1 Specific Objectives

1. To evaluate the performance of chiral matrices in enantiodiscrimination of different analytes by diffusion-NMR.
2. To examine the matrix–analyte and matrix–matrix interactions, along with key experimental parameters that influence frequency and diffusion separations.
3. To perform MD simulations to model the diffusion properties of the diastereomeric complexes.
4. To assess how MD simulation setup parameters affect the accuracy of computed diffusion coefficients and their agreement with experimental trends.
5. To refine representative MD structures using QM calculations to uncover the electronic and structural factors responsible for the observed differences in chemical shifts and diffusion between the enantiomers.
6. To establish a robust workflow for predicting and interpreting enantiodifferentiation trends by QM calculations.

3 Material and Methods

3.1 Experimental Section

The NMR samples were prepared using 120 mM of **1-(R)-BINOL (RBIN)** or **2-(S)-BINOL (SBIN)**, except in cases where **BINOL** concentration was varied, along with 150 mM of **3-(1R,2S)-(-)-N-dodecyl-N-methylephedrinium bromide (DMEB)** or a weighted amount of **3*-PS-750-M** as chiral matrix components. These matrices were employed to discriminate 40 mM enantiomeric mixtures of: **4**–camphor (**CAM**), **5**–mandelic acid (**MA**), **6**–ethyl mandelate, **7**–1-phenylethanol, **8**–1-phenylethylamine, **9**–Mosher’s acid, **10**–2,2,2-trifluoro-1-phenylethanol, **11**–1-(2-fluorophenyl)ethanol, **12**–1-(3-fluorophenyl)ethanol, **13**–ibuprofen, **14**–flurbiprofen, **15**–epichlorohydrin, **16**–glycidol, **17**–propylene oxide, **18**–2-butanol, **19**–3-butyn-2-ol, **20**–1-amino-2-propanol, **21**–pantolactone, **22**–menthol, **23**–carvone, **24**–limonene, **25**–citronellal, and **26**–citronellol. The molecular structures of all investigated compounds are shown in Figure 1.

The samples were analyzed in 5 mm NMR tubes with a final volume of 500 μL , using deuterated chloroform (CDCl_3) as the solvent with 0.03 v/v% tetramethylsilane (TMS) as reference. Except as noted, enantiomeric mixtures of **4**, **5**, **6**, **8**, **9**, **16**, **19**, **20**, **21**, **23**, **24**, and **25** consisted of 70% (*R*)- and 30% (*S*)-enantiomers. For **17**, the composition was 30% (*R*)- and 70% (*S*)-enantiomer, and for **22**, it was 70% (–)- and 30% (+)-menthol.

The NMR measurements were carried out at 298 K on a Bruker Avance III spectrometer operating at 600.17 MHz for ^1H and 564.66 MHz for ^{19}F , using TBI (for ^1H) and TBO (for ^{19}F) probes. The *z*-gradient coils in both probes had a maximum nominal gradient strength of 53.5 $\text{G}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$. The diffusion measurements were performed using the ^1H -Oneshot⁷⁰ and $^{19}\text{F}\{^1\text{H}\}$ -Oneshot⁷¹ pulse sequences with 16 diffusion increments and a gradient strength varying quadratically from 10% to 80% of the maximum nominal value. For each increment, 16 scans and 16 dummy scans were acquired, with 32k (^1H) or 64k (^{19}F) data points. The diffusion time (Δ) and gradient pulse duration (δ) were individually optimized to achieve approximately 80% signal attenuation between the first and last increment.

All 1D NMR spectra were processed using TopSpin 3.7 (Bruker BioSpin), applying zero-filling, Lorentzian line broadening, Fourier transformation, and phase and baseline correction. The diffusion data were processed using GNAT 1.2.3 software⁷², running on MATLAB R2019a. Fourier transformations were applied using a Lorentzian window function, followed by manual and individual phase and baseline corrections. The diffusion coefficients and their associated errors for each species were estimated by fitting the modified Stejskal–Tanner equation using a mono-exponential fit type applied to peaks selected via peak picking. The diffusion coefficient difference between the (*R*)- and (*S*)-enantiomers (ΔD_{RS}), including its propagated uncertainty, and the chemical shift difference ($\Delta\delta_{RS}$) were calculated as follows:

$$\Delta D_{RS} \pm \text{error}_{RS} = (D_R - D_S) \pm \sqrt{\text{error}_R^2 + \text{error}_S^2} \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta\delta_{RS} = \delta_R - \delta_S \quad (2)$$

Figure 1: Molecular structures of the compounds used as matrix components (1-3*) and analytes (4-26) in this thesis. The hydrogens/methyl groups highlighted in red indicate the protons corresponding to the discriminated NMR signals.

3.2 Computational Section

3.2.1 Molecular Dynamics Simulations

A comprehensive set of benchmark simulations was conducted to evaluate the influence of various parameters, including the choice of force field, simulation box composition, simulation length, and the number of replicates. For the optimized system containing (*R*)-MA (RMA) and (*S*)-MA (SMA) and RBIN or SBIN in chloroform as the solvent, the GAFF⁷³ force field was employed with AM1-BCC partial atomic charges^{74,75} from the Antechamber program⁷⁶.

The long-range electrostatic interactions were treated using the reaction-field method, with

a cutoff radius of 1.4 nm applied to the real-space term. The same cutoff distance was used for the neighbor search (Verlet algorithm) and accounting of Van der Waals interactions. All initial configurations were generated using the PACKMOL program⁷⁷.

The best-performing composition consisted of 5 molecules of each **MA** enantiomer and 50 molecules of either **RBIN** or **SBIN**, solvated with 4675 CHCl₃ molecules randomly included in a cubic simulation box. The initial box size was chosen to match the experimental density of CHCl₃ at 298.15 K.

All molecular dynamics (MD) simulations were performed using GROMACS 2018⁷⁸ at 298.15 K. The simulation protocol began with a steepest descent energy minimization until the maximum force fell below 1 kJ·mol⁻¹·nm⁻¹. Subsequently, an isothermal–isobaric (NPT) equilibration was performed for 2 ns (preceded by 500 ps of a preliminary NPT equilibration) to adjust the system to the optimal density and adequate simulation box size for the production simulation steps. Pressure was maintained at 1 bar using the Parrinello–Rahman barostat⁷⁹ with a coupling constant of 2 ps.

The final stage (production phase) consisted of 15 replicates under the canonical ensemble (NVT), each running for 100 ns and preceded by 500 ps of NVT equilibration. Temperature was controlled at 298.15 K using the Nosé–Hoover thermostat^{80,81} with a coupling constant of 0.4 ps. The equations of motion were integrated using a time step of 0.1 fs, and trajectories were saved every 1 ps for further analyses.

The diffusion coefficients (*D*) were extracted from the linear regime of the mean square displacement (MSD) curves using the Einstein relation.⁸² The MSDs were computed by GROMACS, and the results were averaged over all replicates to determine the final *D* for each species. The linear regression was applied to the MSD curve within the time window from 10 to 90 ns.

The VMD program⁸³ was employed to visualize the diastereomeric complexes, calculate their lifetimes, determine their stoichiometry, and measure the distances between the hydrogen atoms at the **MA** stereogenic centers and the center of mass (COM) of **RBIN** or **SBIN**. Additionally, the TRAVIS package⁸⁴ was utilized to compute 3D spatial distribution functions (SDFs) from the concatenated production trajectories.

The diastereomeric homochiral complexes (**RMA** + **RBIN** and **SMA** + **SBIN**) and heterochiral complexes (**SMA** + **RBIN** and **RMA** + **SBIN**) selected for further quantum mechanical (QM) refinement were extracted from the MD trajectories based on their occurrence frequency within specific distance intervals. These intervals were defined according to the distance between the hydrogen atom at the stereogenic center of **MA** and the COM of BINOL.

3.2.2 Quantum Mechanical Calculations

The selected frames from the MD trajectories were further refined using QM calculations, in which the semi-empirical extended tight-binding Hamiltonian GFN2, as implemented in xTB 6.3.2^{85,86} was employed for the initial QM treatment. The CREST 3.0.2 program⁸⁷ was used for the fast and efficient exploration of the conformational chemical space of a large number

of complexes, yielding the final Conformer–Rotamer Ensemble (CRE). The CENSO 1.2.0 algorithm⁸⁸, in combination with ORCA 5.0.4⁸⁹, was employed to refine the CRE in terms of electronic energies, thermochemical corrections, and solvation effects.

Initially, MD configurations were re-optimized at the GFN2-xTB level, and their thermochemical properties were computed based on single-point Hessian (SPH) calculations.⁹⁰ High-energy conformers were discarded, and the remaining structures were filtered based on root-mean-square deviations (RMSD), relative energies, and rotational constants, as implemented in CREST. To further reduce the number of structures, principal component analysis (PCA) combined with k-means clustering was applied, resulting in a representative ensemble for subsequent QM refinement.⁹¹

The clustered ensembles were refined following a four-step protocol designed to compute Gibbs free energies and NMR chemical shifts accurately:

- **Part 0:** Initial electronic energies were obtained via single-point energy (SPE) calculations at the B97-D3/def2-SV(P)+gCP level of theory, incorporating solvation effects using the ALPB implicit solvent model at the GFN2-xTB level.
- **Part 1:** SPE calculations were repeated using the r²SCAN-3c/def2-mTZVPP level of theory with implicit solvation modeled by SMD. Additionally, SPH calculations were performed with the modified rigid-rotor harmonic oscillator (mRRHO) approximation at the GFN2-xTB level (with ALPB solvent) to compute thermochemical contributions and Gibbs free energies.
- **Part 2:** A two-step geometry optimization was conducted. Structures were first pre-optimized at the r²SCAN-3c/def2-mTZVPP level and then fully re-optimized at the higher PW6B95-D3/def2-TZVPP level, both employing SMD solvation. Thermostatistical corrections were computed as in Part 1.
- **Part 3:** Final SPE calculations were carried out at the hybrid meta-GGA level PW6B95-D3/def2-TZVPD with the SMD solvation model. Thermochemical corrections were applied using the mRRHO approach.

NMR chemical shifts (δ) were calculated at the PW6B95-D3/def2-TZVPD level, and the Gibbs free energies of binding were derived for the final ensemble using the same level of theory as in Part 3. All reported NMR properties and binding free energies are presented as Boltzmann-weighted averages over the final conformer ensemble.

Additional benchmarking was performed to evaluate alternative density functionals, basis sets, and solvation models for both SPE and NMR shift calculations. The selected levels of theory were ultimately chosen based on their superior performance in reproducing experimental binding profiles and NMR chemical shift trends.

4 Results and Discussions

4.1 Experimental Studies

The initial goal was to achieve enantiomeric discrimination using chiral micelles formed by the surfactant **3*** in aqueous and organic media. The choice of PS-750-M was inspired by its previous applications in selective monofluorination of indoles and arenes,⁹² as well as its use as a micellar medium in asymmetric catalysis⁵², suggesting its potential as a matrix for MAD. However, **3*** showed limited ability to discriminate enantiomers. Moreover, **3*** is highly sensitive to air, heat, light, and moisture. It requires storage at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and becomes unstable upon removal from cold storage, making sample preparation difficult.

Given these limitations, a different chiral surfactant, **DMEB**, was selected. Previous studies have reported its use as a chiral selector for enantioseparations in electrokinetic chromatography, and its applicability in stereoselective reactions.^{52,93} The literature also suggests that the surfactant and solvent conditions used in this thesis might form reverse chiral micelles,⁹⁴ which may interact distinctly with each enantiomer. Preliminary results with **DMEB** were promising, showing superior enantiodiscrimination compared to **3***. As a result, all subsequent experiments focused exclusively on **DMEB** micelles, and only these findings are discussed in this work.

Initial experiments were dedicated to investigating the separation in the frequency dimension. In this context, **DMEB** micelles successfully discriminated some analytes, such as the **MA** in Figure 2A. However, the observed chemical shift differences ($\Delta\delta_{RS}$) were generally smaller than those achieved with the commonly employed **BINOL**. In other cases, such as the **CAM** (Figure 2B), **DMEB** alone failed to resolve the enantiomers.

Figure 2: ^1H -NMR spectra of an enantiomeric mixture (70% (*R*)- and 30% (*S*)-enantiomer) of (A) **5** and (B) **4**, acquired in the absence and presence of different chiral matrices. The displayed region corresponds to the proton highlighted in Figure 1.

Since the discrimination in diffusion requires prior separation in frequency, without any chemical shift difference, the diffusion coefficients for individual enantiomers cannot be measured, preventing stereoselectivity assessment. To address this limitation, **DMEB** micelles were combined with **RBIN** or **SBIN** to form hybrid matrices and enhance frequency resolution.

As shown in Figure 2B, this strategy enabled successful resolution of **CAM** enantiomers. For **MA** (Figure 2A), pairing **DMEB** with **RBIN** led to loss of separation, whereas combining it with **SBIN** maintained discrimination and slightly increased $\Delta\delta_{RS}$. Overall, the hybrid matrices allowed enantiodiscrimination not achievable with **DMEB** or **BINOL** alone, although the $\Delta\delta_{RS}$ values remained lower than those obtained using only **BINOL**.

Despite this, Figure 3A shows that **BINOL** alone had limited effectiveness in the number of analytes discriminated. **DMEB** alone resolved more compounds, and this number nearly doubled in the hybrid matrices. The **RBIN + DMEB** combination performed better than the **SBIN + DMEB** matrix. These results highlight the superior enantiodiscrimination capability of **DMEB** matrices, mainly when combined with **BINOL**.

Figure 3: Bar plots showing the number of cases in which analytes were discriminated or not in the (A) frequency and (B) diffusion dimensions for each of the employed chiral matrices.

Beyond frequency discrimination, **DMEB** micelles and their hybrid matrices also performed well in the diffusion dimension, achieving ΔD_{RS} values above the experimental error. As shown in Figure 3B, micellar matrices yielded diffusion separation for about three times more analytes than **BINOL** alone, again with **RBIN + DMEB** being the best-performing matrix.

Although the total number of analytes resolved in both dimensions remains modest, **DMEB** systems (especially in hybrid form) were superior to **BINOL** alone and, most importantly, showed consistent stereoselectivity trends based on diffusion, a feature not previously documented for **BINOL**.⁴⁴ One example highlighting this trend is illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4: ^1H -DOSY maps of an enantiomeric mixture of **4** under different conditions: (A) neat mixture, (B) in the presence of **1**, and (C) with **1** and **3**. The sample consists of 70% (*R*)- and 30% (*S*)-**4** in CDCl_3 . The displayed region corresponds to the proton indicated in Figure 1.

As illustrated by the **CAM** case in Figure 4, no frequency differentiation is observed in the absence of any chiral matrix, e.g., both enantiomers show identical chemical shifts (Figure 4A). When only **RBIN** is employed, the stereoisomers become distinguishable in the frequency domain, but still no diffusion separation is detected (Figure 4B). However, full enantiodiscrimination in both dimensions is achieved with the hybrid matrix of **RBIN** and **DMEB** (Figure 4C).

In general, a consistent trend is observed in the frequency dimension with both **RBIN** alone and its combination with **DMEB**, in which the (*R*)-enantiomer displays a lower chemical shift than the (*S*)-form, indicating stronger shielding. Oppositely, with **SBIN**, **DMEB**, or their combination, the trend is reverse (the (*S*)-enantiomer is more shielded).

In the diffusion dimension, **BINOL** alone (Figure 4B) shows no clear selectivity pattern. However, the hybrid matrix **RBIN** + **DMEB** (Figure 4C) demonstrate clear trend for the differentiation, in which the (*S*)-enantiomer has a lower diffusion coefficient than the (*R*)-form, with $\Delta D_{RS} = (0.38 \pm 0.12) \times 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$. This suggests a stronger interaction between the (*S*)-**CAM** and the matrix. A mirrored effect is seen with the **SBIN** + **DMEB** matrix, where the (*R*)-enantiomer shows a lower diffusion coefficient, with $\Delta D_{RS} = (-0.26 \pm 0.12) \times 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$, indicating stronger binding between (*R*)-**CAM** and the matrix.

In the simplest model, where the complex consists of **DMEB-BINOL-analyte**, the observed diffusion coefficients for the analyte signals (D_{obs}) can be described in the fast exchange regime concentration weighted averages (C_{free} and C_{complex}) of the diffusion coefficient of the free enantiomer in solution (D_{free}) and the diffusion coefficient for the diastereomeric complex (D_{complex}), as shown in Equation 3.

$$D_{\text{obs}} = D_{\text{free}} \cdot C_{\text{free}} + D_{\text{complex}} \cdot C_{\text{complex}} \quad (3)$$

Although multiple types of complexes may exist in reality, this simplified model is sufficient

for the purposes of the present discussion. In micellar systems, the chiral surfactant interacts differently with each enantiomer, in which one binds more strongly to the micelle than the other (e.g., the binding constant between **DMEB** and the (*R*)-enantiomer differs from that for the (*S*)-form). As a result, the fraction of the bound state is higher for one of the isomers. This difference is reflected in distinct D_{obs} values, enabling the discrimination between the diffusion coefficients of (*R*)- and (*S*)-enantiomer complexes.

This effect is not apparent when using **BINOL** alone. Even if **BINOL** interacts asymmetrically, the values of D_{free} and D_{complex} remain nearly identical, resulting in minimal variation in D_{obs} , typically within experimental error. Thus, **BINOL** is not employed to induce diffusion differentiation, but rather to enhance separation in the frequency. The diffusion distinction is then enabled by the chiral surfactants, where D_{complex} is more different than D_{free} , so even minor concentration differences are detectable in D_{obs} .

The incorporation of **BINOL** improves separation in the frequency dimension, while **DMEB** ensures reliable diffusion differentiation, with D_{obs} differences exceeding experimental uncertainty. However, as demonstrated in the camphor example, the stereochemistry of **BINOL** in the hybrid matrix also plays a key role in modulating the enantioselectivity.

These stereoselective trends were not limited to **CAM** but were also consistently observed across various analytes, underscoring the robustness and broader applicability of **DMEB** micelles. Figure 5 presents the ΔD_{RS} values for samples with known *ee* of either the (*R*)- or (*S*)-form, when solely **DMEB** micelles and their hybrids are employed as chiral matrices.

Overall, in all samples where ΔD_{RS} exceeded the experimental error, negative ΔD_{RS} values were consistently observed with **DMEB** micelles alone (Figure 5A) or in combination with **SBIN** (Figure 5C), indicating slower diffusion (stronger interactions) of the (*R*)-enantiomers. Although analytes **16** and **21** showed positive ΔD_{RS} values in the presence of **SBIN** + **DMEB**, these remained within the error margin and cannot be reliably interpreted.

In contrast, positive ΔD_{RS} values were observed when **DMEB** was combined with **RBIN** (Figure 5B), indicating stronger binding (lower diffusion) of the (*S*)-enantiomers. These stereoselective patterns remained consistent across different analytes, suggesting that variations in functional groups or molecular skeletons do not significantly influence these trends.

Another noteworthy observation is that the enantiomeric composition of the mixture did not influence the matrix's stereoselectivity. In all cases, the enantiomer exhibiting stronger binding shares the opposite chirality to the employed **BINOL** in the hybrid matrix. For micelles alone, the trend follows the same pattern of the **SBIN** + **DMEB** system. While this behavior remained across different *ee* samples, the ΔD_{RS} magnitude was sometimes affected by the mixture's composition.

Furthermore, the discrimination efficiency also appeared to depend on the spatial proximity between the stereocenter and the binding site. For example, in analytes **23–26**, where the stereocenter is relatively distant from the possible binding site, no enantiodifferentiation was detected with any matrix.

Figure 5: Bar plots showing the diffusion coefficient difference and the associated error for analytes resolved using (A) **3**, (B) **3** with **1**, and (C) **3** with **2**. Blue bars represent mixtures containing 70% (*R*-), red bars correspond to 70% (*S*-) enantiomer, and gray bars indicate racemic mixtures. Analytes marked with * exhibited unresolved enantiomeric NMR signals.

In some instances, such as **MA** with the **RBIN + DMEB** matrix, even though the binding and stereocenter are in close spatial proximity, the enantiodiscrimination was not observed. This may arise from competitive interactions between **BINOL** and micelles, which might affect the enantioseparation.

Moreover, such interactions between the matrix components may also explain the slightly

superior performance of the **RBIN + DMEB** hybrid matrix compared to its **SBIN** combination. The influence of these interactions is evident in titration experiments where a fixed amount of **DMEB** was titrated with increasing concentrations of each **BINOL** (Figure 6).

In these experiments, the observed chemical shift changes suggest that **BINOL** mainly interacts with the polar head region of **DMEB**, as evidenced by the shift of doublet signals associated with this region. Moreover, the interaction strength appeared to differ between the **BINOLs**, in which **RBIN** induced more pronounced shielding effects on the surfactant head signals than **SBIN**. These insights suggest either stronger binding or a higher incorporation of **RBIN** at the micelle interface.

Although diffusion measurements were also conducted, no consistent trends were observed. Therefore, the conclusions regarding matrix component interactions are primarily based on chemical shift changes, which imply that **RBIN** binds more strongly to **DMEB** or is more incorporated into the micelle head region, making the **RBIN + DMEB** matrix a better candidate for enantiodiscrimination.

Figure 6: (A) Full Structure of **3** and (B) the proposed CHIMERA micelles formed between **3** and **BINOL**. The corresponding ^1H NMR spectra of **3** recorded upon increasing amounts of (C) **1** and (D) **2**. The doublet signal corresponds to the methyl protons highlighted with circles in the polar head region of the molecule, while the triplet signal arises from the methyl protons marked with stars in the non-polar tail.

However, even if a stronger **RBIN–DMEB** interaction leads to distinct D_{obs} values, enantiomeric resolution in diffusion remains inaccessible if the corresponding NMR signals are overlapped. This is the case for **MA**, where overlapping signals impede the differentiation of individual diffusion coefficients. The same issue applies to a few other analytes in which no frequency separation was experimentally observed.

In such scenarios, somehow, the matrix components may form strong complexes within themselves, and the micelle complexes may have the potential to interact differently with each enantiomer. However, if these complexes do not have the capability to alter the chemical environment of each enantiomer (i.e., if they do not produce any frequency separation), the distinct interactions cannot be detected by diffusion-NMR, even if a stereoselective binding occurs.

An illustrative example is provided by the behavior of **MA** signals in the hybrid matrix at 120 mM **BINOL** (Figures 2 and 7). At this concentration, frequency separation is only observed with **SBIN**, while the signals remain collapsed with **RBIN**. It is possible that if frequency separation were achieved with **RBIN**, diffusion differences might also be detected.

Figure 7: ^1H NMR spectra of the hydrogen at the chiral center of **5** in an enantiomeric mixture (70% (*R*)- and 30% (*S*)-enantiomer), recorded with a constant concentration of **3** and increasing amounts of (A) **1** and (B) **2**.

A noteworthy observation arises from the chemical shift variations of **RMA** and **SMA** as **BINOL** concentration increases (Figure 7). For **RBIN** (Figure 7A), **SMA** is initially more shielded at low amounts of **BINOL**, but at higher concentrations, **RMA** becomes more shielded. At intermediate concentrations, both enantiomers exhibit identical shifts, leading to

frequency overlap. In contrast, with **SBIN**, **SMA** remains consistently more shielded across all concentrations, and the separation proportionally increases with more **SBIN** amounts.

This behavior suggests that at low **RBIN** concentrations, the shielding effects arise mainly from **DMEB**, as a similar pattern is seen for micelles alone. As **RBIN** amount increases, it progressively modulates the chemical environment, eventually surpassing the shielding effect of **DMEB**. This competitive influence is not observed for **SBIN**, likely due to its similar shielding trend with **DMEB**, resulting in an enhanced frequency separation across all **SBIN** concentrations.

These findings offer insights into matrix–matrix and matrix–analyte interactions, as well as their impact on chemical shifts, diffusion coefficients, and enantioselectivity. However, open questions remain, such as the molecular-level mechanisms driving these trends, the relation between frequency and diffusion separation, and other aspects of these systems that are still difficult to probe experimentally. Therefore, these knowledge gaps emphasize the need for complementary computational studies to further elucidate the stereochemical recognition mechanisms behind these chiral systems.

4.2 Computational Investigations

Given the complexity of the studied chiral systems and the absence of established computational protocols to model enantiodiscrimination as observed in diffusion NMR, a simpler chiral system was chosen for the computational investigations. The goal was first to establish robust simulation methods capable of reproducing experimental trends. Thus, theoretical studies focused on modeling the complex formation between **MA** enantiomers and either **RBIN** or **SBIN**.

It is worth noting that a racemic mixture of **MA** had previously been discriminated using **BINOL** alone.⁴⁴ However, in contrast to the hybrid systems discussed earlier, this required a high **BINOL** concentration (near its solubility limit), yielding only modest diffusion separation (Figure 8). This scenario is not ideal for diffusion-NMR measurements, but it can provide a simplified and informative model for exploring stereoselective interactions computationally.

As shown in Figure 8, **BINOL** alone reproduces the same stereoselective trend observed in the hybrid matrices, reinforcing that **BINOL** plays a key role in determining the overall enantioselectivity. Additionally, in samples with known *ee*, the enantiomer sharing the same **BINOL** chirality appears more shielded in the frequency dimension, while the enantiomer with the opposite chirality exhibits a lower diffusion coefficient. This implies that heterochiral complexes (e.g., **RMA+SBIN**, **SMA+RBIN**) are favored over homochiral ones (**RMA+RBIN**, **SMA+SBIN**). This behavior is similar to that observed for the micellar matrix, reinforcing the suitability of this system as a model for developing computational approaches and mimicking the hybrid matrices.

Figure 8: ^1H -DOSY maps of an enantiomeric mixture of **5** under different conditions: (A) neat mixture, and in the presence of 200 mM of (B) **1**, or (C) with **2**. The sample consists of 70% (*R*)- and 30% (*S*)-**5** in CDCl_3 . The highlighted region corresponds to the proton at the chiral center of the enantiomer.

Here, **RBIN** induces a larger overall decrease in the diffusion coefficients of both enantiomers compared to **SBIN**, suggesting more stable complex formation with **RBIN**. However, **SBIN** achieves greater enantiodifferentiation in diffusion, with $\Delta D_{RS} = (-0.11 \pm 0.04) \times 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$, versus $\Delta D_{RS} = (+0.07 \pm 0.03) \times 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ for **RBIN**. Therefore, a molecular-level understanding of these chiral interactions is essential to explain the observed diffusion and frequency trends, to unravel the relative binding strengths, and to predict the stereoselectivity of chiral resolving agents.

4.2.1 Molecular Dynamics Studies

To gain further insights into the chiral complexation process, MD simulations were conducted to model the behavior of complexes formed between each **MA** enantiomer and **BINOL** stereoisomers. Since no prior studies have reported diffusion coefficients for these chiral compounds, various MD conditions were initially assessed - including the number of molecules, force field, simulation time, and number of replicates — to identify the optimal setup for accurately capturing the experimental trends (Figure 9).

As shown in Figure 9A, simulations using GAFF provided diffusion coefficients more consistent with experimental data than those with OPLS-AA. Overall, systems with five solute molecules yielded more reliable results than those with a single solute molecule. Maintaining the solvent-solute ratio close to experimental conditions, as in System III (approximately 468 CHCl_3 molecules per **MA** molecule), led to more accurate computed diffusion values. Another important observation was that both **RMA** and **SMA** must be simulated in the same box to capture the enantiodiscrimination. Simulating each enantiomer separately (Systems IV and V) resulted in almost indistinguishable diffusion coefficients and did not exceed the error margin. This highlights the significance of competitive binding interactions in capturing stereoselective effects.

Figure 9: (A) Effect of MD system setup on the calculated diffusion coefficients of **MA** enantiomers in the presence of **RBIN**. Diffusion coefficients calculated using GAFF and OPLS force fields for various concentrations: I – 1 (*R*)-**MA** and 1 (*S*)-**MA** / 10 **RBIN** / 935 CHCl_3 ; II – 5 (*R*)-**MA** and 5 (*S*)-**MA** / 50 **RBIN** / 2338 CHCl_3 ; III – same composition as I but with 5 solute copies; IV – 1 (*R*)-**MA** or 1 (*S*)-**MA** / 10 **RBIN** / 468 CHCl_3 ; V – 5 (*R*)-**MA** or 5 (*S*)-**MA** / 25 **RBIN** / 1169 CHCl_3 . Systems IV and V simulate each enantiomer independently. (B) Diffusion coefficients using GAFF for different numbers of replicates. (C) Diffusion coefficients and statistical errors as a function of simulation time for 15 replicates. (D) R^2 correlation coefficients for linear fitting of the mean square displacement (MSD) with increasing numbers of 100 ns replicates.

After selecting the optimal system composition, the impact of simulation time was evaluated. As depicted in Figure 9C, 100 ns simulations were required to achieve statistically meaningful diffusion differences. Although shorter trajectories produced adequate values, they failed to reproduce the correct diffusion ordering. This highlights the need for extended simulations to properly sample molecular motions, especially in systems involving small chiral molecules.

Although it is well-established that longer simulations typically reduce the need for multiple replicates,^{82,95,96} the optimal number of runs for robust enantiodiscrimination was also explored. Figure 9B shows that increasing the number of 100 ns replicates improved the convergence of diffusion values and reduced associated errors. The linear regime of molecular diffusion was confirmed by the high correlation coefficient (R^2), which exceeds 0.990 with 15 replicates (Figure 9D). This indicates a near-ideal MSD behavior and a reliable estimation of the diffusion properties.

With the optimal parameters defined (e.g., force field, system composition, trajectory length, and number of replicates), the final MD simulations were carried out under those conditions to model the diffusion of **MA** in the presence of each **BINOL**. The **MA**:**BINOL** ratios were set to match experimental conditions previously reported to yield optimal separation.⁴⁴ The results are

presented in Figure 10.

Figure 10: (A) Average mean square displacement (MSD) over time for (R)- (blue) and (S)-5 (red) in the absence of each **BINOL** across 15 independent 100 ns MD simulations. MSD in the presence of (B) **1** and (C) **2**. The shaded area indicates the linear fitting region used to calculate diffusion coefficients.

As illustrated in Figure 10, the optimized MD simulations successfully replicated the experimental enantiodiscrimination trends observed by NMR. In the absence of **BINOL** (Figure 10A), both enantiomers showed similar diffusional behavior. Upon addition of **BINOL**, apparent differences emerged, in which in the presence of **RBIN**, **SMA** diffused more slowly than **RMA** (Figure 10B), whereas with **SBIN**, **RMA** showed reduced mobility compared to **SMA** (Figure 10C). These observations suggest the formation of more stable heterochiral complexes.

Overall, the simulations accurately captured **BINOL**'s stereoselectivity toward **MA** enantiomers and correctly reproduced the discrimination patterns. Although these simulations could correctly predict the lowest diffusion properties for the heterochiral complexes, the diffusion coefficients deviate slightly from the experimental values. Notably, achieving such an agreement, with only minor deviations from experiments, remains a challenging task due to the mutual dependence of dynamic properties on various experimental and computational conditions and parameters. For instance, the NMR diffusion coefficients can be significantly dependent on acquisition and processing conditions. Hence, reproducing relative trends rather than absolute values is generally more meaningful. In that regard, the ability of the presented simulations to reproduce the experimental trends validates their predictive power and establishes a computational foundation for further investigation of chiral recognition mechanisms.

In all cases, the reduced diffusion observed for one enantiomer was consistently more pronounced for heterochiral complexes, due to their increased stability. This interpretation is supported by analysis of the MD trajectories, which yielded the mean residence times (e.g., lifetimes) of the diastereomeric complexes.

Specifically, in simulations with **RBIN**, **SMA** exhibit a longer mean lifetime than **RMA**, with a residence time difference of 1.58 ± 0.60 ns. This difference was even more pronounced in the **SBIN** system, where **RMA** complexes remained bound 2.37 ± 0.63 ns longer than those with **SMA**. These findings align well with both experimental and calculated diffusion differences,

reinforcing the conclusion that **SBIN** produces slightly greater enantiodiscrimination, in terms of relative ratio.

To further examine the factors influencing complex stability and lifetimes, the frequency of chiral complex formation at varying **MA:BINOL** ratios was analyzed. Figure 11 summarizes the average occurrence of complexes with different stoichiometries (1:1, 1:2, and 1:3).

Figure 11: (A) Representative molecular structures of **MA-BINOL** complexes with different stoichiometries. (B) Mean frequency of complex formation between each **MA** and **1** (left) or **3** (right).

As shown in Figure 11B, 1:1 complexes clearly predominate, while higher stoichiometries (1:2, 1:3, etc.) are rare or statistically negligible. These findings reinforce the notion that the 1:1 complex is the dominant species in solution and is primarily responsible for the observed enantiodiscrimination. They also help explain the enantiodifferences in the lifetimes of the diastereomeric complexes, offering a molecular-level rationale for the diffusion trends identified via NMR and MD simulations.

Further analysis of the 1:1 complexes, including the spatial distribution functions (SDFs) of **BINOL** around the **MA** enantiomers (Figure 12), reveals that **RBIN** molecules predominantly localize near the carboxyl groups of both **MA** stereoisomers. In both diastereomeric complexes, hydrogen bonding dominates the intermolecular interactions, with similar bonding patterns for both enantiomers.

For **RMA** (Figure 12A), **RBIN** is also frequently found near the hydroxyl group and aromatic ring, indicating additional interaction sites. In contrast, for **SMA** (Figure 12B), **BINOL**

is mainly localized near the hydroxyl group, with fewer alternative binding regions existing. Thus, while both enantiomers form hydrogen bonds with **RBIN**, **RMA** also engages in weaker non-covalent interactions, such as π - π stacking and van der Waals interactions, which are less pronounced or absent (or in a negligible extent) in the **SMA** complexes.

Figure 12: Spatial distribution functions (SDF) of **1** around (A) (*R*)-**5** and (B) (*S*)-**5**, rendered at an isovalue of 0.5. Each panel displays a side view (left) and a front view (right).

Interestingly, the SDF indicates a higher probability of finding **RBIN** near the chiral hydrogen of **RMA** compared to **SMA**. This proximity likely contributes to stronger shielding effects in the NMR spectrum, consistent with the experimentally observed lower chemical shift for **RMA**. In contrast, the SDF for **SBIN** is less discriminative, showing similar spatial patterns for both **MA** enantiomers.

To further correlate NMR chemical shifts with MD data and explore the relationship between diffusion and shielding, structural analyses of dominant 1:1 complexes were performed. Specifically, the distances between the chiral hydrogen in each **MA** and the **BINOL** center of mass (COM) were calculated, providing insight into the local chemical environments of each stereoisomer in the presence of the resolving agent.

The highest number of complexes is formed at $H_{MA} \cdots \text{BINOL}_{COM}$ distances between 5.0 Å and 7.5 Å, where Van der Waals interactions, hydrogen bonding, and π - π interactions are all feasible in both homochiral and heterochiral complexes. Within the range of 4.0 Å to 12.5 Å, heterochiral complexes show a greater number of contacts. In contrast, at shorter distances (< 4.0 Å), homochiral pairs are slightly more frequent. For distances beyond 12.5 Å, the chiral selectivity becomes less pronounced due to the attenuation of the intermolecular interactions and increased solvent effects, thus reducing enantiomeric differentiation.

Intermolecular distances in the range of 2.5 to 12.5 Å are particularly informative for these chiral complexes. Typically, at larger distances, where heterochiral complexes dominate, the chiral hydrogen tends to be positioned farther from the **BINOL** molecules. Oppositely, at shorter distances, where homochiral complexes are more frequent, the hydrogen atom is located closer to **BINOL**, experiencing a greater shielding effect, which may explain the lower chemical shifts observed in the NMR experiments.

Overall, MD simulations effectively captured the dynamic behavior of chiral complexes, reproducing key experimental trends and offering molecular-level insights into enantioselective interactions. However, additional QM calculations are required to refine further the understanding

of chemical shifts, binding energies, and interaction modes that drive chiral recognition between **MA** and **BINOL**.

4.2.2 Quantum Chemical Studies

To gain a more detailed molecular-level understanding and obtain quantitative insights into chemical shifts and complex stabilities, selected snapshots from MD simulations were refined using QM calculations. Structures were chosen based on the $H_{\text{MA}} \cdots \text{BINOL}_{\text{COM}}$ distance, previously identified as a key indicator of enantioselective binding. According to this criterion, 7103 heterochiral and 578 homochiral complexes involving **RBIN**, and 8414 heterochiral and 54 homochiral complexes with **SBIN** were extracted for further QM refinement (Figure 13A).

After refinement, the final ensembles included 6 homochiral and 16 heterochiral complexes for **RBIN**, and 5 homochiral and 11 heterochiral for **SBIN**. In both cases, the orientation of the chiral hydrogen relative to the **BINOL** aromatic rings was a critical factor in enantiodifferentiation. For instance, in the lowest-energy **RBIN** complexes, the hydrogen of **RMA** in the homochiral complex (Figure 13B) points toward the **BINOL** rings, while in the heterochiral complex (Figure 13C), it points toward the solvent. As a result, the hydrogen atom of **RMA** experiences a higher electronic density from the **BINOL** aromatic rings, resulting in a more shielded chemical environment in the magnetic field compared to **SMA**, consistent with the NMR observations.

Figure 13: (A) Schematic workflow for QM refinement of chiral complexes extracted from MD snapshots. (B) Representative homochiral and (C) heterochiral complex structures involving **1**. The highlighted atoms indicate the hydrogen at the chiral centers.

In the low-energy structures of **SMA** with **RBIN**, the stabilization primarily arises from hydrogen bonding. In contrast, in the **RMA**–**RBIN** complexes, the π – π stacking and van der Waals interactions are the main stabilizing forces. The relatively weaker interactions in the homochiral complexes explain their shorter lifetimes in MD simulations and the correspondingly higher diffusion coefficients (weaker binding) observed in the NMR experiments.

To confirm this, NMR chemical shifts and Gibbs free energies of binding were calculated for all refined complexes. As shown in Table 1, the predicted values agree well with experimental trends. The lower Gibbs free energies of the heterochiral complexes confirm their greater thermodynamic stability, reinforcing the conclusion that they exhibit longer lifetimes and are more strongly bound than their homochiral counterparts.

Table 1: Calculated Gibbs free energies of binding ($\Delta G_{\text{binding}}$) and their enantiomeric differences ($\Delta\Delta G_{\text{binding}}$), in kcal/mol, along with calculated ($^{QM}\delta_{MA}$) and experimental chemical shifts ($^{Exp.}\delta_{MA}$) in ppm, for both homochiral and heterochiral complexes.

Complexes	$\Delta G_{\text{binding}}$	$\Delta\Delta G_{\text{binding}}$	$^{QM}\delta_{MA}$	$^{Exp.}\delta_{MA}$ ⁴⁴
(<i>R</i>)-MA + (<i>R</i>)-BIN	-21.871	+1.393	4.803	5.182
(<i>S</i>)-MA + (<i>R</i>)-BIN	-23.264		5.667	5.190
(<i>R</i>)-MA + (<i>S</i>)-BIN	-23.076	-1.149	5.504	5.236
(<i>S</i>)-MA + (<i>S</i>)-BIN	-21.927		3.601	5.228

The energy differences between homochiral and heterochiral complexes are relatively small, around 1–2 kcal/mol (Table 1). This magnitude aligns with previously reported values in the literature,^{97–99} reflecting the modest energetic distinctions typical of complexation between enantiomeric species. Additionally, although the calculated NMR shifts for heterochiral complexes are slightly underestimated, the simulations still accurately represent the experimental trends. Recent studies have demonstrated that machine learning approaches can further refine these chemical shift predictions, obtaining shifts with minor deviations from the experimental data.^{100–102} However, such techniques fall beyond the scope of the present thesis.

To ensure the robustness of this computational protocol, benchmarking studies were also conducted using different theoretical methods to assess the reliability of both the binding free energy and chemical shift calculations.

For the QM benchmarking, the performance of various implicit solvation models, including SMD, CPCM, and openCOSMO-RS, was tested and produced comparable results, with only minor deviations among them. Due to its slightly better agreement with experimental NMR data, the SMD model was selected for subsequent calculations. Subsequently, several DFT functionals were tested for their performance in predicting NMR chemical shifts, as shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14: Calculated chemical shifts for the hydrogen atom at the chiral center of (*R*)-**5** (left) and (*S*)-**5** (right) using different theoretical levels in the presence of **1**. Structures were pre-optimized at the $r^2\text{SCAN-3c}/\text{def2-mTZVPP}$ level and fully optimized at the $\text{PW6B95-D3}/\text{def2-TZVPP}$ level. Functionals in PART3 were used with the def2-TZVPD basis set and the SMD solvation model for chloroform.

Among the functionals evaluated, PW6B95 provided the best agreement with experimental shifts, although all tested methods produced reliable and consistent results for the shielding

effects. In other words, each level of theory correctly captured the shielding effect induced by the employed **BINOL** on the enantiomer of opposite chirality (Figure 14) and successfully reflected the experimentally stereoselectivity.

The slight underestimation in the chemical shift of the more shielded enantiomer may result from an overestimation of the local electronic density introduced by the **BINOL** aromatic rings. Nonetheless, it is essential to note that the ability of DFT methods to resolve such minor differences in chemical shifts is pushed to the limits of their accuracy.

Importantly, reproducing experimental trends, rather than absolute values, is more informative for understanding the molecular basis of chiral recognition. In this context, the multiscale computational strategy employed here successfully captures the enantiodifferentiation patterns, offering valuable mechanistic insights into the stereoselective interactions governing these complexes and establishes a systematic workflow for predicting interactions with other resolving agents.

Overall, for further details on the experimental procedures, computational methods, results, and discussions presented in this document, readers are encouraged to consult the original publications and their supporting information, available at: [10.1002/anie.202418508](https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.202418508) .

5 Conclusions

In conclusion, the experimental strategy presented in this work demonstrates that hybrid matrices in MAD provide a promising, rapid, cost-effective, and versatile approach for determining absolute configuration via diffusion-NMR. A wide range of analyte samples (featuring diverse functional groups, molecular skeletons, and enantiomeric compositions) were successfully discriminated using **DMEB** chiral micelles combined with **BINOL**. Although specific analytes exhibited only modest or no separation (particularly when the stereocenter is distant from the binding site), the hybrid matrix system remains a reliable approach for enantioanalysis.

This thesis also revealed how interactions between matrix components impact enantiomer separation, especially in the frequency dimension. The data indicated that **BINOL** localizes in the polar region of **DMEB** micelles and that competitive interactions may exist. Notably, the results presented here enable the future use of our approach to determine the *AC* of unknown enantiomers by observing diffusion behavior in the presence of a CHIMERA. The enantiomer exhibiting lower diffusivity (stronger interaction) shares the opposite chirality to the employed **BINOL**.

Moreover, the integration of experimental and computational methods provided molecular-level insight into the stereoselectivity of **BINOL** toward the enantiomers. Through extensive molecular dynamics simulations with multiple replicates, we successfully reproduced experimental diffusion trends and identified key parameters, including complex lifetimes, stoichiometries, and structural arrangements, to rationalize the chiral recognition. These findings were further supported by quantum mechanical calculations, which further validated the binding energies and shielding effects responsible for enantiodiscrimination.

Overall, this thesis establishes a robust and adaptable strategy for studying chiral recognition by combining experimental and simulation approaches. The methodology provides a foundation for the rational design of new chiral matrices and can be extended to explore stereoselectivity in systems involving other enantiomers.

Ultimately, the advances reported here contribute to the development of more accurate and accessible spectroscopic methods for *AC* determination, a persistent challenge not just for NMR and computational chemistry but also in other scientific fields and industrial applications. This work lays the foundation for designing the next generation of matrices capable of enhancing enantiomer separation, resolving challenging systems, and even expanding computational insights for the micellar chiral environments.

6 References

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